

Bacteriological Profile and Antimicrobial Susceptibility Pattern of Lower Respiratory Tract Infections in COVID Positive Patients

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Abstract: The COVID-19 pandemic caused by severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-Cov-2) has grown into the biggest medical emergency of the twenty-first century. The proportion of COVID-19 patients with acute respiratory bacterial co-infection and the etiological agent is crucial to ensure the responsible use of antibiotics and to minimize negative consequences of overuse of antibiotics. This study was carried out to isolate aerobic pathogenic bacteria causing lower respiratory tract infections in COVID Positive Patients and to study their antimicrobial susceptibility pattern. A total of two hundred respiratory samples of COVID positive patients having lower respiratory tract infections were tested during a period of three years between April 2020 to March 2023.

Rate of LRTI amongst COVID Patients was found to be 20.70% in our study. *Streptococcus pneumoniae* (22%) and *Acinetobacter spp* (19.5%) were the most common bacterial species isolated in COVID patients. This study demonstrated that bacterial co-infection were the common complications seen in hospitalized COVID-19 patients in our hospital setup.

Keywords: Lower Respiratory Tract Infections (LRTIs), COVID Positive Patients, *Acinetobacter spp*, *Streptococcus pneumoniae*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*

Introduction:

COVID-19 was a pandemic which resulted in more than 11,500,000 cases and 500,000 fatalities.^[1] The COVID-19 pandemic has grown into the biggest medical emergency of the twenty-first century. As of 24th September 2023, India has recorded 60,00,000 deaths and a total of 77,00,00,000 confirmed cases of COVID-19.^[2] Like other viral pneumonias, COVID-19 hospitalised patients frequently develop bacterial and fungus infections. The prevalence and profile of secondary infections in COVID-19 Indian patients is not very well understood. While antibiotics are ineffective for treatment of COVID-19, they are prescribed in patients with suspected COVID-19 for a variety of reasons. This includes difficulty in ruling out bacterial co-infection and the possibility of bacterial secondary infection during the course of the illness. Extrapolating from concerns of an increase in mortality in patients with bacterial super infection during COVID pandemics, several guidelines advocate the use of empirical antibiotics for patients with severe COVID-19. However, this assumption raises concerns of antibiotic overuse and subsequent harm associated with bacterial resistance.

The treatment of COVID-19 patients with acute respiratory bacterial co-infection is crucial to know the etiological agent and the appropriate antibiotics to minimize negative consequences of overuse. In addition, this knowledge could have a significant impact in refining empirical antibiotic management guidelines for patients with COVID-19.^[3]

The present study was carried out to understand the etiology and antimicrobial resistance profile of secondary bacterial respiratory infections in COVID positive patients.

Materials & Methods:

This study was carried out over a period of three years from April 2020 to March 2023 in the Department of Microbiology, MGM Medical College and Hospital, Kamothe, NaviMumbai. A total of 200 Respiratory Samples of COVID Positive Patients having Lower Respiratory Tract Infections were tested.

All the samples were processed as per standard bacteriological procedures.^[4,5] The etiological agents were identified by studying their colony characters on Blood agar, Chocolate agar, MacConkey agar and doing a battery of biochemical tests.

Antimicrobial susceptibility pattern of all isolated pathogenic bacteria was determined by Modified Kirby Bauer disc diffusion method on Muller Hinton agar. The diameter of zone of inhibition was measured and susceptibility pattern was interpreted according to the CLSI guidelines.^[6] Following 1st line antibiotics for Gram Positive Bacteria were used Co-Trimoxazole (COT), Cefuroxime (CXM), Ciprofloxacin (CIP), Cefoxitin (CX), Cefazolin (CZ), Gentamicin (GEN), Amoxyclav (AMC), Clindamycin (CD), Azithromycin (AZM), Penicillin-G (P) and Roxithromycin (RO) among 2nd line antibiotics were Meropenem (MRP), Cefotaxime (CTX), Levofloxacin (LE), Clarithromycin (CLR) and Netilmicin (NIT). Following 1st line antibiotics for Gram Negative Bacteria were used Cefuroxime (CXM), Ciprofloxacin (CIP), Cefazolin (CZ), Gentamicin (GEN), Amoxyclav (AMC), Tobramycin (TOB), Cefotaxime (CTX), Amikacin (AK), Cefaperazone (CPZ), Ofloxacin (OF) and Ceftazidime (CAZ) among 2nd line antibiotics were Ceftazidime/Tazobactam (CAT), Ceftriaxone/Sulbactam (CFS), Piperacillin/ Tazobactam (PIT), Cefotaxime/Clavulanic acid (CEC), Meropenem (MRP), Aztreonam (AT), Ertapenem (ETP), Polymyxin B (PB), Ceftriaxone/Salbactam (CIS), Tigecycline (TGC) and Levofloxacin (LE).

Results & Observations:

A total of 200 Respiratory Samples of COVID Positive Patients having Lower Respiratory Tract Infections were tested. They were Sputum 193 (96.5%), Endotracheal Secretions 5 (2.5%), and Bronchoalveolar lavage 2 (1%). Rate of LRTI amongst COVID Patients was found to be 20.70%.

TABLE 1. Age Wise Distribution of COVID Positive Patients having LRTI (n=200)

Age in Years	No. of Patients	% of patients
< 18	04	2%
18 - 40	54	27%
40 - 60	62	31%
60 & above	80	40%

Graph 1 depicts the age wise distribution of COVID Positive Patients having LRTI.

Graph 1: -Age Wise Distribution of COVID Positive Patients having LRTI (n=200)

Maximum number of COVID Positive Patients were belonging to the age group of 60 & above.

TABLE 2. Sex Wise Distribution of COVID Positive Patients having LRTI (n=200)

Sex	No. of Patients	% of patients
Male	134	67%
Female	66	33%

Graph 2 depicts the sexwise distribution of COVID Positive Patients having LRTI.

Graph 2: -Sex Wise Distribution of COVID Positive Patients having LRTI (n=200)

Bacterial LRTI was more prevalent in Males (67%) as compared to Female (33%)

Graph 3 depicts the spectrum of various bacteria causing LRTI among COVID patients.

Graph 3: Spectrum of Bacteria isolated having LRTI amongst COVID Patients (n = 200)

It is observed that, the most predominant Gram-Negative Bacteria are *Acinetobacter spp*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. And the most predominant Gram-Positive Bacteria are *Streptococcus pneumoniae*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Streptococcus viridans*.

TABLE 3. Most and Least Effective Antibiotics against Gram Positive Bacteria isolated from COVID Patients having LRTI (n = 79)

Sr. No.	Gram Positive Bacteria Isolated from COVID Positive Patients having LRTI	Most Effective Antibiotics	Least Effective Antibiotics
1.	<i>Streptococcus pneumoniae</i>	1 st Line- GEN, AMC, CIP, CX, CZ	AZM, P, RO, CXM
2.	<i>Streptococcus viridans</i>	1 st Line- CZ, AMC, CX, CIP, GEN	AZM, CXM, RO, P
		2 nd Line- CTX, LE, CLR,	

		NIT, MRP	
3.	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	1 st Line- AMC, CX, CIP, GEN, CZ	AZM, RO, P, CXM
		2 nd Line- NIT, CLR, LE, MRP, CTX	

Gram positive bacteria when subjected to antibiotic sensitivity test it was found that amongst the 1st line antibiotics Gentamicin, Amoxyclav, Ciprofloxacin, Cefoxitin and Cefazolin were the most effective antibiotics whereas among higher (2nd line) antibiotics Cefotaxime, Levofloxacin, Clarithromycin, Netilmicin and Meropenem were most effective. Roxithromycin, Cefuroxime, Azithromycin and Penicillin showed high level of resistance.

TABLE 4. Most and Least Effective Antibiotics against Gram Negative Bacteria isolated from COVID Patients having LRTI (n = 121)

Sr. No.	Gram Negative Bacteria Isolated from COVID Positive Patients having LRTI	Most Effective Antibiotics	Least Effective Antibiotics
1.	<i>Acinetobacter spp</i>	1 st Line- GEN, AK, CTX, CIP, OF	CZ, AMC, CXM
		2 nd Line- PB, LE, MRP, PIT, CFS, AT, ETP, CIS, CAT, CEC, TGC	
2.	<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	1 st Line- CTX, GEN, AK, OF, CIP	CZ, <u>AMC, CXM</u> (inherently Resistant)
		2 nd Line- TGC, PB, LE, MRP, ETP, PIT, CFS, AT, CAT, CEC, CIS	

3.	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	1 st Line- CTX, CIP, OF, GEN, AK	CZ, <u>CXM,AMC</u> (inherently Resistant)
		2 nd Line- PB, MRP, TGC, LE, PIT, CAT, AT, CFS, CEC, ETP, CIS	

Gram negative bacteria when subjected to antibiotic sensitivity test it was found that amongst the 1st line antibiotics Gentamicin, Amikacin, Cefotaxime, Ciprofloxacin and Ofloxacin were most effective whereas in higher (2nd line) antibiotics Polymyxin B, Meropenem, Aztreonam, Ertapenem, Levofloxacin, Ceftazidime/Tazobactam, Cefaperazone/Sulbactam, Cefotaxime/Clavulanic acid, Ceftriaxone/Sulbactam, Tigecycline and Piptaz were most effective. Cefazolin, Cefuroxime and Amoxyclav showed high degree of resistance.

Discussion:

Coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19), caused by the Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus 2 (SARS-Cov-2), has spread worldwide and has escalated into the largest health crisis of the 21st Century. ^[1] Just like other viral infections, bacterial and fungal infections are common complications seen in hospitalized COVID-19 patients.

A total of 200 bacterial isolates were obtained from the lower respiratory samples of COVID Positive Patients. Rate of LRTI amongst COVID Patients was found to be 20.70%. In a similar study done by Pengcheng Liu, *et.al*, ^[7] conducted at Department of Clinical Laboratory, Children's Hospital of Fudan University, National Children's Medical Center, Minhang District, Shanghai China has reported the rate of LRTI amongst COVID Patients was 23.30%.

In the present study out of all pathogen isolated, Gram-Negative Bacteria were the predominant pathogen (60%) than Gram Positive Bacteria (40%). In another study done by Sonam Vijay, *et.al*, ^[8] Gram-Negative Bacteria were the predominant pathogen (78%) than Gram Positive Bacteria (22%). In a study done by Jean-Francois Llitjos, *et.al*, ^[9] Gram-Negative Bacteria were the predominant pathogen (34%) than Gram Positive Bacteria (30%), in another study carried out in non-COVID patients done by Salman Khan, *et.al*, ^[10] Gram-Negative Bacteria were the predominant pathogen (77.61%) than Gram Positive Bacteria (22.39%). This shows that Gram-Negative Bacteria are more frequently associated with respiratory infection, irrespective of their COVID status.

In the present study, Table 1 and Graph 1 presents data about the age distribution of COVID Patients. It was observed that maximum number of COVID Positive Patients were belonging to the age group of above 60 years. In a similar study conducted by Paolo Gaibani, *et.al*, ^[11] The maximum number of COVID Positive Patients were from the age group of above 60 years. This shows that the age group of people over 60 years are more prone to acquire infection. This may be because at the age of 60, people are active and hence are exposed to infection. They may have a lower immunity due to progression of age.

In the present study, Table 2 and Graph 2 presents data about gender distribution of COVID patients. It was observed that the bacterial LRTI was more prevalent in Males (67%) as compared to Female (33%). In a similar study conducted by Paolo Gaibani, *et.al*,^[11] The bacterial LRTI was more prevalent in Males (71%) as compared to Female (29%). This shows that males have a higher risk of getting infection than female, which may be due to they are more exposed to the outdoors.

In our study, Graph 3 presents data about the rate of isolation of bacterial species in LRTI samples of COVID Patients, they were *Streptococcus pneumoniae* (22%), followed by *Acinetobacter spp* (19.5%), *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (15%), *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (12.5%), *Streptococcus viridans* (11%), *Enterobacter spp* (10.5%), *Staphylococcus aureus* (5%), *Pseudomonas spp* (1%), *Citrobacter spp* (1%), *Escherichia coli* (1%), *Coagulase Negative Staphylococcus spp* (1%) and *Streptococcus pyogens* (0.5%). However, in a study conducted by Paolo Gaibani, *et.al*,^[11] The rate of isolation of bacterial species in LRTI samples of COVID Patients were *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (25%), followed by *Streptococcus pneumoniae* (12%), *Enterobacteriaceae* (12%), *Staphylococcus aureus* (11%), *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (7%), *Enterococcus spp* (5%) and *Prevotella* (4%). In a study conducted by Salman Khan, *et.al*,^[10] The rate of isolation of bacterial species in LRTI samples of non-COVID Patients were *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (27.41%), followed by *Haemophilus influenzae* (26.25%), *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (13.89%), *Streptococcus pneumoniae* (11.58%), *Staphylococcus aureus* (10.81%) and *Escherichia coli* (10.06%). This shows that the spectrum of bacteria varies because of the various geographical conditions in different places.

In the present study, for gram positive bacteria Gentamicin, Amoxyclav, Ciprofloxacin, Cefoxitin and Cefazolin were the most effective antibiotics whereas among higher (2nd line) antibiotics Cefotaxime, Levofloxacin, Clarithromycin, Netilmicin and Meropenem were most effective. Roxithromycin, Cefuroxime, Azithromycin and Penicillin showed high level of resistance.

In our study, for gram negative bacteria Gentamicin, Amikacin, Cefotaxime, Ciprofloxacin and Ofloxacin were most effective whereas in higher (2nd line) antibiotics Polymyxin B, Meropenem, Aztreonam, Ertapenem, Levofloxacin Ceftazidime/Tazobactam, Cefaperazone/Sulbactam, Cefotaxime/Clavulanic acid, Ceftriaxone/Sulbactam and Piptaz were most effective. Cefazolin, Cefuroxime and Amoxyclav showed high degree of resistance.

Conclusion:

One of the most severe complications of COVID patients was super added bacterial lower respiratory tract infections and this was leading to death of many patients. Hence, this study was carried out to study the antimicrobial resistance profile of secondary bacterial respiratory infections in COVID positive patients. During COVID-19 pandemic, there was over prescribing of antibiotics due to panic situation. Rampant use of antibiotics may lead to redundance of drugs and emergence of multi drug resistant bacteria. Hence, we recommend to switch over to culture & sensitivity guided antibiotic therapy once the microbiology report is available. This will reduce the antibiotic burden and development of drug resistant pathogens.

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